

Additional file 6.

Frequency distributions of length of *msp1* block 2 sequence for assembled and unassembled sequences. Dummy reads created from 964 *msp1* block 2 sequences were assembled using Velvet. The frequency distributions of the lengths of the original *msp1* block 2 sequences are shown for successfully assembled (black line, n = 902) and unassembled (red line, n = 62) sequences are shown (sequences lengths are grouped with a bin width of 5 bp).